

**FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH
CONTRACEPTIVE-USE AMONG
FEMALE UNDERGRADUATES IN A
SELECTED UNIVERSITY IN OGUN
STATE, NIGERIA.**

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ABSTRACT

- **Background:** With the emerging increased prevalence of sexual relationships that end in intercourse among young unmarried and married individuals proliferating society with most times results that end in poor pregnancy outcomes, two major concerns are raised; how this phenomenon impact on population desired family size and abortion prevalence. In the absence of intentional sexual abstinence among this population, there should be serious considerations given to safe sexual practice that guarantee control on unwanted pregnancy. It is conceptually considered that comprehensive use of contraceptive by female undergraduates is essential if the projected increase in sexual and reproductive poor health outcomes in the country is to be halted with its associated reduction in poor pregnancy outcomes associated with present low contraceptive prevalence, more defined studies needs to be conducted to fully understand the dynamics of contraceptive-use among the at-risk population.
- **Objective:** This pilot study was undertaken to identify factors associated with contraceptive use among female undergraduate and to determine predictors of contraceptive-use among this at-risk population.
- **Methodology:** This was a pilot study adopting the cross-sectional study design on 30 purposively sampled female undergraduates aged 17-27years in Olabisi Onabanjo University, Ogun state. Validated questionnaire developed sought to measure respondents' socio-demographic characteristics, personal-level disposition, environmental-level disposition and their sexual behaviour. Data collected were Analysed by the computer-assisted statistical software SPSS version 24 and derived frequency distribution of items which were transformed to weighted aggregates to provide summary of descriptive statistics of means and standard deviations to permit computations of Pearson correlation and logistic regression analysis for test of hypothesis where p-value of ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.
- **Results:** Results showed that Outcome expectation and attitudinal disposition had a stronge association with contraceptive use with 53.3% of respondents displaying positive attitudinal disposition towards contraceptive use. The study similarly revealed that 70% of the respondents had above average knowledge regarding sexual and reproductive health issues and consequences of unprotected sexual intercourse.
- **Conclusion:** Information-adequacy, probably from multiple sources and access to sexual and reproductive health education invariably accounted for the observed attitudinal disposition towards safe sexual practices. Most importantly, the preferred source of information in the study was from family members. Therefore, more interactive conversations relating to sexuality issues should be initiated and encouraged at home as this lays a better foundations to contribute in their decisions-making towards safe sexual practices.

OUTLINE

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INTRODUCTION

- Sexual and reproductive health (SRH) challenge depends on several indicators of which contraceptive-use is one of them. Contraceptive may be viewed as the hub on which other indicators associated with SRH rest (Ofonime, 2017). The indicators are fertility rate, contraceptive-prevalence, maternal mortality and HIV prevalence. Appropriate use of contraceptive is capable of preventing Sexually Transmitted Infections (STIs), unintended pregnancies, unplanned abortion and its complication (Yen and Martin, 2013), maternal deaths, poverty due to large family size, and school dropout (Awusabo-asare, Bankole and Kumikyere, 2008) for undergraduate females with age ranging from 16 to 25 years thereby limiting their potentials for productive contribution in society.

STATEMENT PROBLEM

- Evidence has shown there is increased sexual activities among young people (Adadow, Shamsudeen, Thomas and Yakubu, 2015; Gaetano, Abdul-Rahman, De-Coninck and Annika, 2014) with a low contraceptive prevalence (Akintayo, Akin-Akintayo, Adanikin and Ade-ojo, 2015; Henry, Sekandi, Hassard and Frederick, 2016; Okpokumoku, Nwose and Nwajei, 2017; Ahmed, Ibrahim, Mohammed, Yahaya and Patrick, 2016). an indication of risky sexual behaviour.
- This consensus predisposes young people to sexual and reproductive health issues including unintended pregnancies, early child bearing, unsafe abortions, sexually transmitted infections (STIs) with the brunt of poor sexual behaviour bearing on females (Adogu, Udigwe, Nwabueze and Onwasigwe, 2014).

STATEMENT PROBLEM

- Undergraduate females special needs in relation to their sexual life is their ability to have sexual satisfaction in order to impress their sexual partners with the hope of having sustained relationships (Manlove, Ryan and Kerry, 2006). The desire to sustain their relationships outweighs their ability to consider consequences of unhealthy sexual behaviors.
- Studies have revealed low level of knowledge about contraceptives (Akinbode, 2016), poor access to SRH services (Chandra-Muoli, 2014), attitude of healthcare workers (Ezihe, 2014; Rutaramwa, Kabagenyi, Wandera, Jhamba Akiror and Nviri, 2015) as predictors of contraceptive use among young people.
- Sexual and reproductive health, and its detrimental effect when not properly managed is of great public health importance. One of many ways of managing SRH of females is through promoting safe sex practices where sexual abstinence is not practicable. Promoting safe sex practices can be achieved through adequate sexuality education targeted at improving knowledge and access to reproductive health services. The consequences of poor SRH are increased prevalence of STIs, increased unplanned and unwanted pregnancies, increased abortion rates, increased maternal mortality rate (Stover and Ross 2010), complications due to abortions, financial burden especially for those from poor backgrounds, social stigmatisation (if infected with HIV) and in most cases, females may not be able to continue with their educational pursuit or experience a setback (Aigbiremolen, 2014).

OBJECTIVE

- **OBJECTIVE;** This pilot study was undertaken to identify factors associated with contraceptive use among female undergraduate and to determine predictors of contraceptive-use among this at-risk population..

JUSTIFICATION

- In spite of studies revealing low level of knowledge of contraceptive-use (Tien, 2006), poor access to SRH services (Awusabo-Asare, 2006; Chandra-Muoli, 2014) and attitude of healthcare workers (Ezihe, 2014; Rutaramwa *et al*, 2015), other studies identified high level of knowledge with a decrease in contraceptive use (Akintayo *et al*, 2015; Ahmed *et al*, 2016, Adadow *et al*, 2015) as predictors influencing the use of contraceptive among female undergraduates, the problem still persists.
- Although Akinbode (2016) identified low level of knowledge about contraceptive as a factor responsible for low contraceptive use among female undergraduates of Olabisi Onabanjo university, little is known about other factors that could predict the use of contraceptive among this population of interest. The lack of documented evidence about this university is unclear but it is presumed that it may be due to low responses as a result of the sensitive nature of the topic.
- This study is therefore intended to identify the gap in literature.

METHOD

- This was a pilot study adopting the cross-sectional study design on 30 purposively sampled female undergraduates aged 17-27 years in Olabisi Onabanjo University, Ogun state. Validated questionnaire developed sought to measure respondents' socio-demographic characteristics, personal-level disposition, environmental-level disposition and their sexual behaviour. Data collected were analysed by the computer-assisted statistical software SPSS version 24 and derived frequency distribution of items which were transformed to weighted aggregates to provide summary of descriptive statistics of means and standard deviations to permit computations of Pearson correlation and logistic regression analysis for test of hypothesis where p-value of ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

- Results showed that Outcome expectation and attitudinal disposition had a stronger association with contraceptive use with 53.3% of respondents displaying positive attitudinal disposition towards contraceptive use. The study similarly revealed that 70% of the respondents had above average knowledge regarding sexual and reproductive health issues and consequences of unprotected sexual intercourse.

CONCLUSION

- Information-adequacy, probably from multiple sources and access to sexual and reproductive health education invariably accounted for the observed attitudinal disposition towards safe sexual practices. Most importantly, the preferred source of information in the study was from family members. Therefore, more interactive conversations relating to sexuality issues should be initiated and encouraged at home as this lays a better foundations to contribute in their decisions-making towards safe sexual practices.

FUTURE WORK

- This presentation was a pilot study carried out among female undergraduates. With the results revealed, the presenter is currently working on a research with same population on “predictors of contraceptive-use among female undergraduates in Olabisi Onabanjo University, Ogun state Nigeria. The aim is to assess predictors with using larger sample size so as to obtain information that will bring about intervention and also predict the sexual and reproductive health status of Nigerians.

**○THANK YOU FOR
LISTENING**